

COGNITIVE APPROACH TO SYNONYMIC RELATIONSHIP IN TERMINOLOGY (ENGLISH AND UZBEK)

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ABSTRACT

The term terminology in modern linguistics is used in different meanings. In accordance with the structure of this term (it is a combination of the word the term and the Greek logos - the word, the doctrine), it denotes the doctrine of terms, the section of linguistics (lexicology) dealing with the study of terms, or the corresponding scientific (scientific and applied) discipline. However, in this sense, the term is rarely used. In recent times, some linguists have used the term "terminology" to describe this concept.

Terminology in linguistics is often called a set of terms used in a particular language or in a certain sphere of people's activities. In the latter meaning, i.e. to denote the concepts of a particular area of knowledge or any field of activity, it is often used a composite term "terminological system" or the complex formation of the "terminology-based system" created on its base.

In the understanding of the term as a unit of terminology, or an element of a terminology system, the views of linguists differ significantly, which is reflected in the definition (explanation) of this concept by different scientists.

It is quite clear that the term, as well as any other sign language unit, has an exponent or signifier, and content, or signified, but the view of the exponent and content of the

terminological sign is different for researchers.

An exponent of a terminological unit is traditionally considered to be a word, although most modern linguists regard not only a single word as an exponent of the term, but also a combination of different words, more precisely, a phrase. In the definition of the term as the closest generic concept, some scientists call, respectively, the word (see, for example, the works of RA Budagov, AA Reformatsky, MI Fomina, NM Shanskii), others - word or combination of words, word combination, expression, compound name, etc. (see the works of OS Akhmanova, BN Golovin, AV Kalinin, VI Kodukhov, R. Yu. Kobrin, and others). Now, it seems, no one doubts that the term can be not only a single word, but also a phrase, although there is no complete clarity on the

question of which particular word combinations can be terms, and which are not terms. There is no unity of opinion on the question of the morphological properties of the term, its partial affiliation. Some linguists recognize the terms only nouns and substantive phrases, i.e. word-combinations with a reference word-a noun, others do not consider this attribute mandatory for the term, i.e. recognize the meaningful words of different parts of speech and the phrases based on them, called compound terms. In modern linguistics, the first point of view prevails, which seems more convincing.

According to T.I. Arbekova for example, the "language form of expression of terms are nouns and phrases based on them".[1] According to her, "terms are words and phrases of strictly nominative function, namely, a certain type of nouns and phrases based on them," is a strictly nominative part of special and general vocabulary and phraseology in the form of nouns and word-combinations on their base & quot ;. The legitimacy of such a view of the term is confirmed, in particular, by the fact that "nominative function in the strict sense is possessed only by certain categories of nouns and stable combinations based on them." As for the words of other parts of speech, they have an indirect relation to terminology. According to BN Golovin, terms are limited to "the properties of parts of speech: the adjective, the verb, the adverb are included in terminological relations not independently, but through the noun of the noun." [2]

A distinctive feature of the meaning of the term, its signified, is that it has a professional meaning, designates a certain

scientific, production, technical, etc. concept. This is recognized by all linguists dealing with the problem of the term, although the connection of the term with the concept of linguists is treated differently. In accordance with this, in the understanding (and definition) of the term, several concepts are distinguished:

- 1) the term is a word (or a phrase) that calls the concept, i.e. performs nominative function (GO Vinokur, EM Galkina-Fedoruk, etc.);
- 2) the term is the word that expresses the concept, i.e. performs an expressive, expressive function (AA Reformatsky, SM Burdin, etc.);
- 3) the term recognizes the word denoting the concept, i.e. fulfilling a significative function (EI Amosenkova, RN Infant'eva, NN Levinskii, etc.);
- 4) a term is a word that defines a concept, i.e. fulfilling a definitive function (V. V. Vinogradov, S. A. Askoldov, etc.).

The reason for this was that the first approximations to terminology had normalization as a primary objective. Great pains were taken to strive for totally unambiguous communication through standardization. This signified univocity or one-to-one reference between term and concept. The fact that the majority of terms designate concepts that represent objects in a specialized knowledge field meant that such an objective seemed possible to achieve. Nevertheless, it soon became apparent that this was more a desideratum than a reality.

As has often been observed, terminology means many things to many people. Terminology is a word that can either begin with an upper or lowercase letter. When terminology begins with a small t, it

refers to the units in any specialized knowledge field. When it begins with a large T, it refers to the study of specialized language. As a rule, Terminology theories can be classified as either prescriptive or descriptive. General Terminology Theory (GTT), which has the virtue of being the first theoretical proposal in this area, is essentially prescriptive in nature. As shall be seen, the theories that subsequently arose in reaction to the GTT are descriptive, and show an increasing tendency to incorporate premises from Cognitive Linguistics since they focus on the social, communicative, and cognitive aspects of specialized knowledge units. The vision that they offer is more realistic because they analyze terms as they actually are used and behave in texts. One might say that these new theories are representative of a cognitive shift in Terminology. Numerous synonymous words and phrases are an integral part of the lexical diversity of the language. But it should be noted that synonymy is an unfavorable phenomenon in cases of exact communication, in particular in the field of medicine.

Medical translation is work with highly specialized text, which is characterized by strict style restrictions and high percentage of terminology. Medical text brings together a large number of various genres: an extract from a medical history, an article from a medical encyclopedias, indications for the use of the medicinal product. When the translation of this type of text is of great importance to maintain accuracy, as misinterpretation of information can lead to unpredictable consequences for human health. But today the medical language is the richest of

all technical languages in terms of synonyms, which often leads to the emergence of various problems in the field of translation and not only. Synonymy of terms (from the Greek synonymia - the same name) represents is a type of semantic relationship based on the ability of different terminological units denote one special concept, expressing various additional signs of the concept, emotional or stylistic coloring, use and compatibility with others terminological units.

There are several reasons that contribute to the appearance and the use of synonyms in medical vocabulary. For example, in situations when different groups of researchers almost simultaneously discovered or invented the same term and did not verify its existence in medical literature. The next reason may be a tendency

use of foreign terms, even if there is the corresponding name in the native language. There are a large number of synonyms in the English language.

This was facilitated by the fact that in its development the English language has undergone double influence of the Germanic language and Latin. Thanks to this fact today almost all concepts in English have several words that

often refer to two different registers of use. Therefore, perhaps one of the biggest problems when translating from English language is the correct use of case.

Here are some pairs of English synonyms found under translation of medical texts:

Delivery - birth

Haemorrhoids - Hemorrhoids

Haemorrhage - bleeding

Piles - Hemorrhoids

In addition, synonymy is found in the field of scientific terms. This the fact suggests that there is a need to standardize the medical language. Some of the most significant examples are: delivery - childbirth, parturition - generic act, childbirth - generic act, thigh bone - femur, scapula - shoulder blade, cranium - skull, coccyx - tailbone, uterus - womb, doctor - physician - medical practitioner.

It is clear that finding synonyms in terminology is very difficult. But in the Uzbek language we can come across abundant terminological synonyms in the field of medicine. I highly recommend for learners to get acquainted with the book "Lotin tili va tibbiyot terminologiyasi" which comprises numerous example medical terms. I will convey some of them below in Uzbek:

Apendis - ko'richak - o'simta

Appendicitis - a serious medical condition in which the appendix becomes inflamed and painful.

Alkogolizm - ichkilikbozlik

Alcoholism - an addiction to the consumption of alcoholic liquor or the mental illness and compulsive behavior resulting from alcohol dependency.

Anemiya - kamqonlik

Anemia - a condition marked by a deficiency of red blood cells or of hemoglobin in the blood, resulting in pallor and weariness.

Antibiotik - dori

Antibiotic - a medicine (such as penicillin or its derivatives) that inhibits the growth of or destroys microorganisms.

Bavosil - gemmoroy

Hemorrhoid - a swollen vein or group of veins in the region of the anus.

Gripp - shamollash

Flu - short for influenza.

Dieta - parhez

Diet - the kinds of food that a person, animal, or community habitually eats.

Mongoloidizm - Daun sindromi

down syndrome - a congenital condition characterized by a distinctive pattern of physical characteristics including a flattened skull, pronounced folds of skin in the inner corners of the eyes, large tongue, and short stature, and by some degree of limitation of intellectual ability and social and practical skills. It usually arises from a defect involving chromosome 21, usually an extra copy (trisomy-21).

O'simta - o'sma

Tumour - a swelling of a part of the body, generally without inflammation, caused by an abnormal growth of tissue, whether benign or malignant.

Ambliyopiya - oftalmoskop

Amblyopia - a tool to observe impaired or dim vision without obvious defect or change in the eye.

Reanimatsiya - jonlantirish

Resuscitation - the action or process of reviving someone from unconsciousness or apparent death.

Oftalmolik - ko'z shifokori

Ophthalmologist - a specialist in the branch of medicine concerned with the study and treatment of disorders and diseases of the eye.

Doktor - shifokor

Doctor - a qualified practitioner of medicine; a physician.

Names of drugs which can be synonyms to each other:

Rebetol - Ribavarine - Ribamidil - Ribapeg

Xenalten - Listata

Zilt - Listab - Lopirel

Terms are types of words: all terms are words or made up of words, but not all words are terms. Specifically, a term is a word that is typically used in a specialized field. For example, 'sternum' is the medical term for the bone at the front of the ribcage. This is especially found in medicine and other sciences.

To summarize, while all terms are words, not all words are terms. 'Word' is the basic, neutral word for things that represent concepts. Terms, however, are specialized words, and they tend to be more formal because of their common associations.

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